

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION

MuSpinSim: spin dynamics calculations for muon science.

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I. THE MUSPINSIM INPUT FILE

This supplementary information describes how to provide an input to MuSpinSim and it shows the inputs used for the examples provided in the main paper. It should be noted that as the software evolves, new keywords may be added and existing keywords may change in name or behaviour. Up-to-date documentation for future versions will be available on the MuSpinSim website¹.

A. How to input keyword values in MuSpinSim

In MuSpinSim mathematical expressions, functions and variables can be used as keyword values. This feature allows for the keyword values to:

- Be used to access some meaningful mathematical or physical constants in place of numbers. For example, one can write `10.0*MHz` as an applied magnetic field, and it will immediately be converted to the equivalent field in Tesla for an ALC resonance, as `MHz = 1/(2*muon_gyr)`, with the gyromagnetic ratio of the muon, `muon_gyr = 135.5388 (in MHz/T)`.
- Be used to automatically generate large ranges of values for some common use cases. For example, the keyword `time` stores all the times at which the simulation should be performed. It is a common requirement to want to acquire hundreds or thousands regularly spaced time points, which can be done by using something like `range(0, 1, 100)` to create 100 equally spaced time points going from 0 to 1 microseconds.
- Be used to insert variables whose values we want to fit. For example one might define a hyperfine interaction tensor as a function of two parameters, then fit those parameters to find the optimal tensor that explains an experimental result.

Expressions allow use of the operators `+`, `-`, `*`, `/` and `^` for exponentiation. Parentheses `(` and `)` can be used. Strings, if used, must be enclosed in double quotes `''`. User-defined constants are currently not allowed: the only types of user-defined variables that can be used are the ones for fitting. By default, all keywords in which expressions can be used allow the following constants:

- `pi`: ratio of a circle and its diameter
- `e`: base of the natural logarithm

- `deg`: conversion factor between radians and degrees, equivalent to $180/\pi$
- `inf`: infinity

and the following functions:

- `sin(x)`: sine
- `cos(x)`: cosine
- `tan(x)`: tangent
- `arcsin(x)`: inverse of the sine
- `arccos(x)`: inverse of the cosine
- `arctan(x)`: inverse of the tangent
- `arctan2(y, x)`: inverse of the tangent taking two arguments as (sine, cosine) to resolve the quadrant
- `exp(x)`: exponential with base e
- `log(x)`: natural logarithm
- `sqrt(x)`: square root

These are all reserved names and can't be used as variable names.

Some keywords accept an arbitrary amount of lines. This is different from keywords like `hyperfine`, that only take three lines so that the user can write a full 3×3 matrix. Keywords that allow multiple rows are meant to allow the user to define ranges of values. When a range of values is defined, three things can happen:

- one range must always exist and will be specified as the `x_axis` of the system. This will be the range of values that appears on the first column of the output files. This is usually time, but it can also be, for example, field.

- some ranges are specified as `average_axes` and will be averaged over. This means that calculations will be carried for each value in these ranges and then they will all be summed over, and only the average will be printed out. A typical example of an axis to average over is `orientation`, to perform powder averages.
- any range that is not specified in the previous two groups automatically means that the software will print out a different file for each value.

When using ranges, remember that the number of calculations to perform grows very quickly with them. If one for example asked for an average over 100 different orientations, and to print out a file for each of 20 possible fields and 10 different temperatures, that would result in $100 \times 20 \times 10 = 20,000$ individual simulations, and $20 \times 10 = 200$ files. The software does not have any specific safeguards against going overboard with them, but is very easy if working on a simple desktop machine or laptop to just overwhelm its capabilities if one uses big ranges carelessly. `MuSpinSim` is reasonably well optimised and can be very fast for simple calculations, but complex systems and large ranges can make for very resource-intensive simulations.

B. A list of input keywords for `MuSpinSim`

1. `spins`

Keyword	<code>spins</code>
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

```
spins
mu e 2H
```

A list of the spins to be used in the system. This has to include a muon (`mu`) and can contain one or more electrons (`e`). If only one electron is present, it will be the one all hyperfine couplings are with by default. Atomic species refer to the nuclei; so, for example, if you're trying to model the

interaction of a muon with a paramagnetic electron on an iron atom, you want to use `e`, not `Fe`; the actual spin is that of an electron, not a nucleus! In addition, in case of multiple strongly coupled electrons that can be treated as a single spin greater than 1/2, the isotope syntax can be used too, so for example `2e` represents two electrons in a triplet state, acting as a single particle with the same gyromagnetic ratio as the electron, but spin 1. The default isotope is the most common one that has a non-zero spin. Other isotopes may be specified by writing the atomic mass as an integer before the symbol. By default, this is a muon and an electron.

2. *name*

Keyword	<code>name</code>
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

```
name
mysystem
```

A prefix to use for all files saved in this simulation. By default is `muspinsim`.

3. *polarization*

Keyword	<code>polarization</code>
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	default, <code>longitudinal</code> ; <code>transverse</code>
Allows functions	default

Example:

```
polarization
longitudinal
```

This keyword indicates the direction along which the muon should be polarized when starting the simulation, as well as the direction along which the polarisation will be measured. It can be specified as a vector, and multiple values are allowed. The constants `transverse` and `longitudinal` are useful short-hands for the direction of the X axis and the Z axis, respectively. Unless specified otherwise, the magnetic field is aligned along the Z axis. The default value is `transverse`.

4. *field*

Keyword	<code>field</code>
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	default, <code>MHz</code> ; <code>muon_gyr</code>
Allows functions	default, <code>range</code>

Example:

```
field
  0
  1*MHz
  2*MHz
  4*MHz
```

A single field, or range of magnetic fields, in Tesla, to simulate. These can be scalars or vectors; if scalars, the field will be assumed to be aligned with the Z axis. If only the start and end values are specified in the function `range`, it expands to 50 values by default. The default value is zero.

5. *time*

Keyword	<code>time</code>
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	default
Allows functions	default, <code>range</code>

Example:

```
time
    range(0, 1, 100)
```

A time or range of times, in microseconds, to run a simulation. Used by default as the `x_axis`. If only the start and end values are specified in the function `range`, the expands to 50 values by default. The default value is `range(0, 10, 101)`.

6. `x_axis`

Keyword	<code>x_axis</code>
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

```
x_axis
    field
```

Which range to use as the X axis for the simulation's output files. Must be a keyword that accepts a range and it must be specified as a range in this input file. When fitting, this is also assumed to be the X axis of the data to fit, and the range specified for this keyword is overridden by the fitting data. By default it is time.

7. `y_axis`

Keyword	<code>y_axis</code>
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

y_axis
integral

What to save as the Y axis of the simulation's output files: if the muon's polarization ([asymmetry](#)) or its integral over time, taking into account the exponential decay with the particle's half-life ([asymmetry](#)). By default is [asymmetry](#), and can generally be ignored unless one is interested in Avoided Level Crossing experiments, which need [integral](#). When set to [integral](#), the [time](#) keyword is ignored and can not be the [x_axis](#).

8. *average_axis*

Keyword	y_axis
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

average_axis
orientation
polarisation

Any keywords that should have an average carried out over them (if they include a range of values). By default it is just [orientation](#). Any axes with a range that aren't either [x_axis](#) or included here are automatically used for different files.

9. *orientation*

Keyword	orientation
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	default
Allows functions	default, zcv , eulrange

Example:

```
orientation zxz
  45*deg 0 90*deg 1.0
  90*deg 30*deg 60*deg 2.0
```

One or more orientations to use for the crystallites that make up the system. Used to define powder averages. The rows can come in a number of ways:

- two numbers are interpreted as two polar angles θ and ϕ , defining only the direction of the Z axis of the new system. This setting is recommended only for powder averages in which only the Z axis matters. A typical example is an Avoided Level Crossing calculation with both the magnetic field and the muon polarization aligned along the Z axis.
- three numbers are interpreted as Euler angles defining a new frame. If there is no argument specified after orientation, the convention used is ZYZ. As seen in the example, it is possible to specify it to be ZXZ instead.
- four numbers are interpreted as Euler angles as above, plus one weight. The weights don't need to add up to one (they will be normalised). In this case, any average over these orientations will be weighted; otherwise, the weights will be ignored.

Two helper functions are provided to generate automatically ranges of orientations for powder averages. `zcw(N)` creates N or more polar angle pairs using the Zaremba-Conroy-Wolfsberg algorithm to cover the sphere. It is cheap but only usable in cases in which polar angles are sufficient. `eulrange(N)` creates a regular grid of Euler angles with appropriate weights. This covers the space of all possible orientations in 3D but can become a lot more expensive very quickly.

10. *temperature*

Keyword	<code>temperature</code>
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	default
Allows functions	default, <code>range</code>

Example:

```
temperature
```

```
220.0
```

Temperature in Kelvin of the system. This is used to determine the initial density matrix of the system, as every spin that is not the muon is put in a thermal state. In the case of dissipative systems, the temperature is used to determine the coupling to the thermal bath. By default, temperature is set to infinity. A warning: both density matrices and dissipative couplings for finite temperatures are only calculated approximately, based on the individual Hamiltonians for each spin which only account for the applied magnetic field. In other words, these approximations are meant for high field experiments, and break down in the low field regime. Therefore, caution should be used when changing this variable or interpreting the resulting simulations.

11. *fitting_variables*

Keyword	<code>fitting_variables</code>
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	default, <code>muon_gyr</code> , MHz
Allows functions	default

Example:

```
fitting_variables
x
y 1.0 0.0 5.0
```

Variables used to fit to the experimental data. If these variables are present, the calculation is assumed to be a fitting and the `fitting_data` keyword must be present too. The first letter in each row is the name of the variable; optionally, it can be followed in order by the starting value of the variable, the minimum bound, and the maximum bound (by default 0, -inf and +inf). It is important to notice that while expressions are accepted in the definition of value, minimum, and maximum, these can not contain the name of other variables.

12. *fitting_data*

Keyword	fitting_data
Allows multiple rows	Yes
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	none
Allows functions	load

Example:

```
fitting_data
    load('results.dat')
```

Block of data to fit. Must have two columns: the first one is the [x_axis](#) (for example, time), while the second is the expected result of the simulation. The function [load](#) can be used to load the data from an ASCII tabulated file on disk, as long as it has only two columns. **Note that the data must be normalized properly to match the conventions of MuSpinSim's output, so for example it must start from 0.5 at $t = 0$ (as that's the moment of the muon before it has had any time to evolve).**

13. *fitting_method*

Keyword	fitting_method
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

```
fitting_method
    lbfgs
```

Method used to fit the [fitting_data](#). There are two methods currently available: [nelder_mead](#), which is the default one; and [lbfgs](#).

14. *fitting_tolerance*

Keyword	fitting_tolerance
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

```
fitting_tolerance  
    1e-4
```

Tolerance for the fitting. Used as the `tol` parameter in Scipy's `scipy.optimize.minimize` method; exact meaning depends on fitting method. Check the Scipy documentation for further details.

15. *experiment*

Keyword	experiment
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	No
Allows constants	N/A
Allows functions	N/A

Example:

```
experiment  
    alc
```

A convenience keyword that sets a number of other parameters to reproduce certain experimental setups. Possible values are: `alc` `zero_field`. `alc` sets up an Avoided Level Crossing experiment where the polarization is longitudinal, `field` is `x_axis` and `integral` is `y_axis`). `zero_field` sets up a zero field experiment where `field` is 0 and `polarization` is `transverse`.

16. *zeeman*

Keyword	zeeman
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	Default
Allows functions	Default

Example:

```
zeeman 1  
      2.0 2.0 0
```

Add a Zeeman coupling term specifying a local magnetic field, in Tesla, for a given spin. This coupling will be on top of the standard coupling with the external magnetic field from the laboratory, that always applies to all spins. The argument is the index of the coupled spin. Indices count from 1.

17. *hyperfine*

Keyword	hyperfine
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	Default
Allows functions	Default

Example:

```
hyperfine 1  
      100 10 10  
      10 100 10  
      10 10 100
```

Specify a hyperfine tensor, in MHz, for a given spin. A hyperfine tensor couples the spin with one electron in the system. If there is only one electron, then only the index of the non-electron spin can be indicated. If there is more than one electron in the system, more than one index must

be indicated, and the second index must refer to an electron. The tensor must be written with three numbers per line. The argument (here 1) represents the index of the coupled spin. A second argument specifying the index of the electron is only obligatory if the system has more than one electron. Indices count from 1. Note that the block is always composed of three rows, but this is not interpreted as a range.

18. *dipolar*

Keyword	dipolar
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	Default
Allows functions	Default

Example:

```
dipolar 1 2
  0 1 1
```

Specify a dipolar coupling between two spins. This is given by a vector connecting them, in Angstrom. The coupling tensor will be then calculated based on the known gyromagnetic ratios of those spins. The two arguments are the indices of the coupled spins. Indices count from 1.

19. *quadrupolar*

Keyword	quadrupolar
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	Default
Allows functions	Default

Example:

```
hyperfine 3
  100 10 10
```

```
10 100 10
10 10 -100
```

Specify a quadrupolar coupling for a spin by using an Electric Field Gradient tensor in atomic units (as returned by for example the DFT software CASTEP). The argument is the index of the spin. The coupling will then be calculated by using the known values of angular momentum and quadrupole moment for each spin. Spins with zero quadrupole moment (like hydrogen) will have zero coupling regardless of what is specified in this term. Indices count from 1. Note that the block is always composed of three rows, but this is not interpreted as a range.

20. *dissipation*

Keyword	dissipation
Allows multiple rows	No
Allows expressions	Yes
Allows constants	Default
Allows functions	Default

Example:

```
dissipation 1
0.5
```

Add a dissipation term for a given spin, which switches the system to using the Lindblad master equation instead of regular unitary quantum evolution. The dissipative term will cause random spin flips that decohere the system and drive it towards a thermal equilibrium state (determined by the temperature). The dissipation term is given in MHz. Indices count from 1.

CAUTION: Lindbladian matrices can be not diagonalizable. This functionality does not yet account for that, so it could fail in some cases.

II. EXAMPLES

A. Modelling of μ SR experiments on crystalline NaF

1. *MuSpinSim* input file for modelling a ZF μ SR experiment on NaF.

The is assumed to be at 210K and for a range of time of 8 microseconds.

```
name
  NaF_ZF-dip_muSR
spins
  mu F F
dipolar 1 2
  0.82731493 0.82731493 0
dipolar 1 3
  -0.82731493 -0.82731493 0
temperature
  210
time
  range(0, 8.0, 1000)
```

2. *MuSpinSim* input file for modelling a ZF μ SR experiment with dissipation on NaF.

```
name
  NaF_ZF-dip_muSR
spins
  mu F F
dipolar 1 2
  0.82731493 0.82731493 0
dipolar 1 3
  -0.82731493 -0.82731493 0
dissipation 2
  0.03
dissipation 3
```

```
0.03
temperature
210
time
range(0, 8.0, 1000)
```

3. *MuSpinSim input file for modelling a TF μ SR experiment with dissipation on NaF.*

```
name
NaF_TF-dip_muSR
spins
mu F F
field
0.0127 0.0127 0.0127
dipolar 1 2
0.82731493 0.82731493 0
dipolar 1 3
-0.82731493 -0.82731493 0
dissipation 2
0.03
dissipation 3
0.03
temperature
210
time
range(0, 8.0, 1000)
```

B. Modelling of Avoided Level Crossing (ALC) experiments di-iron subsite Analogues of [FeFe]-Hydrogenase

1. Details of CASTEP DFT simulations

All hyperfine tensor calculations were conducted using the ab-initio software package CASTEP, version 20.0². Unit cells of $\text{Fe}_2(\text{pdt})\text{CO}_4(\text{PMe}_3)_2$, containing two molecules and a muonium atom were used for each bridge structure, with a $1 \times 1 \times 1$ k-point grid and a 850 eV plane wave cut-off. The exchange correlation functional used was RSCAN³, the pseudopotentials were ultrasoft on-the-fly generated pseudopotentials. All structures were geometry optimised to a 0.05eV/Ang tolerance under these conditions before computing the hyperfine tensors for the muoniums, which are shown below:

$\text{Fe}_2(\text{pdt})\text{CO}_4(\text{PMe}_3)_2\text{-RB}$

226.0231	-18.2510	-62.8243
-18.2510	239.7670	-37.4381
-62.8243	-37.4381	261.8144

$\text{Fe}_2(\text{pdt})\text{CO}_4(\text{PMe}_3)_2\text{-LB}$

230.5622	-17.2011	-66.1431
-17.2011	256.8179	-38.3972
-66.1431	-38.3972	272.6007

2. MuSpinSim input files for the simulation of ALC results in $\text{Fe}_2(\text{pdt})\text{CO}_4(\text{PMe}_3)_2\text{-RB/LB}$

$\text{Fe}_2(\text{pdt})\text{CO}_4(\text{PMe}_3)_2\text{-RB}$

name

C13H24Fe204P2S2-RBmeta

spins

e mu

hyperfine 2

226.0231	-18.2510	-62.8243
-18.2510	239.7670	-37.4381

-62.8243 -37.4381 261.8144
experiment
 alc
field
 range(0.2, 2.0, 200)
temperature
 10
orientation
 zcg(40)

$\text{Fe}_2(\text{pdt})\text{CO}_4(\text{PMe}_3)_2\text{-LB}$

name
 C13H24Fe204P2S2-LBmeta
spins
 e mu
hyperfine 2
 230.5622 -17.2011 -66.1431
 -17.2011 256.8179 -38.3972
 -66.1431 -38.3972 272.6007
experiment
 alc
field
 range(0.2, 2.0, 200)
temperature
 10
orientation
 zcg(20)

REFERENCES

¹<https://muon-spectroscopy-computational-project.github.io/muspinsim/>.

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- ³A. P. Bartók and J. R. Yates, en“Regularized SCAN functional,” *The Journal of Chemical Physics* **150**, 161101 (2019).